

Scurvy in Hudson's bay (1746-1747)

by Henry Ellis

Henry Ellis participated in the search for the Northwest Passage. During the crew's wintering at Hudson Bay, an outbreak of scurvy occurred, which Ellis later described in a book written after the voyage. This document focuses on the sections of his account that deal with scurvy.

A Voyage to Hudson's-Bay by the Dobbs Galley and California in the Years 1746 and 1747, for Discovering a North West Passage, by Henry Ellis:

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Biographies of Henry Ellis:

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henry_Ellis_\(governor\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Henry_Ellis_(governor))

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/40580542>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/23521777>

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A Voyage to Hudson's-Bay by the Dobbs Galley and California in the Years 1746 and 1747, for Discovering a North West Passage,¹ by Henry Ellis

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THE
SECOND PART:

CONTAINING,
A clear and circumstantial Account
of the *Last Expedition*, by the
Dobbs-Galley, and the
California, in 1746, and
1747.

THE Ships bought by the *Committees* were one of *One Hundred and Eighty Tons* Burthen, called the DOBBS-GALLEY; and the other of *One Hundred and Forty Tons*, which was called, the CALIFORNIA. Each of these Vessels was perfectly well repaired and strengthened, and in all Respects fitted, as well as could be desired, for the Voyage on which it was intended they should proceed. They had also a sufficient Quantity of Provisions, military and naval Stores, with such Goods as were fit for Presents to the Inhabitants of the Countries that might be discovered, put on board them in sufficient Quantity, and as good in their respective Kinds, as it was possible to procure...

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THE Ships fitted out for this Expedition, fell down from *Gravesend*² to the *Hope*, on the 20th of *May*, 1746; and lay there till the 24th of the same Month...

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ON the 5th of *October*, we had much Ice in the Creek, and by the 8th it was fast froze. Until the 30th we had Snow, Frosts, and moderate Weather, alternately, and that Day being his present Majesty's Birth-Day, we hoisted our Colours, and

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1 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Northwest_Passage

2 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gravesend>

fired twenty-one Guns. The 31st, *Hayes River*³ was froze quite hard, so that now we had some Experience of what was to be expected from an *Hudson's-Bay*⁴ Winter...

BESIDES these small Sledges, we had others more large and strong, for carrying great Weights; these were of the same Form as those before described, but ten or twelve Feet long, and three wide, they require twenty or thirty Men yoked to draw them. The first Time of their going to the Factory, was the 8th of *December*, from whence they brought two Casks of Brandy for Christmas Cheer, which Season is generally celebrated in this Country by the *English* (so easily are the best Institutions corrupted) by immoderate Drinking, and all the Folly and Madness that attend it...

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<https://archive.org/details/voyagetohudsonsb00inelli/page/196/mode/2up>

THE Language which these People speak, is somewhat guttural⁵ in the Pronunciation; is but for all that, neither very harsh, nor altogether unpleasant; they have but few Words, but those are very significant; and the Method they have of expressing new Ideas, by Words composed, from compounding the Qualities of those Things, to which they would give Names, is very easy and intelligible; so that the *English* find no Sort of Difficulty, either in learning or speaking it. There is no doubt, therefore, that if they were so inclined, they might easily teach these poor People the Use of Letters, the Principles of Morality, and the Doctrines of Religion; which would be equally charitable and generous;

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3 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hayes_River

4 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hudson_Bay

5 Guttural.

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Guttural>

for if they were so instructed, they might not only live much better themselves, but their Trade also would turn to much greater Account; and it would infallibly imprint on their Minds, a very high Reverence, and a very tender Affection for the *British* Nation.

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As I have so fair an Occasion, I cannot avoid mentioning a very strange Maxim of Policy, which prevails much amongst them; and which is, that of suffering, or rather obliging their Women to procure frequent Abortions, by the Use of a certain Herb common in that Country, and not unknown here; that they may in some Measure be eased of that heavy Burthen they feel, in providing for a helpless Family. Something of this sort the *Dutch* inform us was practised by the Natives of the Island of *Formosa*⁶ when they were Masters of it; nor is this at all more barbarous, than a Custom still used in *China*, of suffering Children when born, to die for Want of Food, from the same Principle of brutal Oeconomy. They differ also from almost all other Nations in another Particular, which is their manner of making Urine; for here the Men always squat down, and the Women stand upright. It is now high Time to return to our own Affairs, and to inform the Reader, how they were conducted, in such a Country as I have described this to be, and in which, notwithstanding all our Precautions, we felt many Inconveniences.

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THE bringing two Cases of Brandy from *York-Fort*⁷ for *Christmas-Cheer*, has been already mentioned; as well as the Design of it, which was to make merry with; but the Consequences were extremely fatal. The People had been healthy enough, before this Season of Mirth⁸ came; but indulging themselves too freely, they were soon invaded by

6 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Formosa_\(disambiguation\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Formosa_(disambiguation))

7 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fort_York

8 Mirth. Gladness or gaiety as shown by or accompanied with laughter.

the SCURVY, the constant Attendant on the Use of Spirituous Liquors. It is a melancholy, but withal a necessary Task, to describe the Progress of this foul and fatal Distemper. Our Men when first seized with it, began to droop, to grow heavy, listless, and at length indolent to the last Degree: A Tightness in the Chest, Pains in the Breast, and a great Difficulty in breathing, followed; then ensued livid Spots upon the Thighs, swelled Legs, Contraction of the Limbs, putrid Gums, Teeth loose, a Coagulation of the Blood upon and near the Back Bone, with Countenances bloated and sallow. These Symptoms continually increasing, 'till at length, Death carried them off, either by a Flux or a Dropsy. Those Medicines, which in other Countries are generally used with good Effects, proved entirely ineffectual here; for Unctions and Fomentations, when applied to contracted Limbs, afforded no Relief; fresh Provisions indeed, when we could get them, did somewhat; but the only powerful and prevailing Medicine, was TAR-WATER; and the steady Use of this saved many, even after the Disease was far advanced; when, as I before observed, all other Medicines lost their Efficacy, and were tried to no Purpose; and yet, as far as we could observe, this salutary Drink operated no other Way than by Urine.

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THOSE *English* that reside here constantly, are little, if at all, exposed to this cruel Distemper; which they attribute to the constant Use of **SPRUCE BEER**;⁹ a Liquor

9 Spruce beer; See discussions of vitamin C content in spruce and fir trees
<https://doi.org/10.3138/cbmh.7.2.161>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamadermatol.2014.4582>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.99.2563.125.a>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.98.2545.325.a>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.98.2541.242.a>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.98.2541.241>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.98.2536.132.a>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.97.2520.354.c>
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.92.2376.35.b>

See also extracts at the end of this text, on p.14.

that has the same, or, perhaps, higher *Qualities*, than *Tar-Water*; and by plentiful drinking of which, the People at the four Factories of *Churchill*, *York-Fort*, *Albany*, and *Moose-River*, enjoy so good a State of Health; that tho' in Number about an Hundred, seven Years have sometimes past without their burying so much as a Man; which is a Circumstance, so very remarkable, that I persuade myself, none of my Readers will blame me, for recording it.

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WHEN the Crews of both Vessels were in this deplorable Condition, no Sollicitations were spared to the Governor of *York-Fort* for Relief; and there was the more Reason to have hoped, these Applications would not have proved so fruitless as they did; considering that all we asked, was only to allow the *Indians*, to supply us with fresh Provisions. I say allow; for they would willingly have done it, had there not been an Interposition of ill Offices to prevent it. It is a strange Insinuation, that Cruelty of Christians toward Christians, prevented that Relief, which *Indian* Humanity would otherwise have certainly afforded. But what shall I say? The *Indians* were charged not to come near us, or to furnish us with any thing; and this out of a tender Regard for them; because, we had a contagious Distemper amongst us, which might communicate itself to them, and to their Families; and, besides, we were equally Enemies to them, and to the *English*. Intimidated by these Insinuations, the *Indians* would not approach our Dwellings; but why such Insinuations were thrown out, unless, in Obedience to Orders the Governor durst not disobey, is not easy to discover. It could not be from any Fear of Want; for with Venison, Partridge, Fish, &c. the *Indians* both could and would have supplied us in Plenty, without Prejudice to the Factories. Neither could it be from any self-interested Motives, with Regard to Trade; for these were not trading

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but home *Indians*; the former were at this Time retired far within Land; the latter dwell constantly about the Factories, and their proper Employment is to procure Provision. But these Insinuations proved afterwards detrimental to Trade, as well as to us; for spreading to a great Distance, they had such an Effect on the Minds of these poor ill-judging People, that but very few came down to *York-Fort*, the next Season. The sole View, therefore, in this matter, was the distressing us, and that View was thoroughly answered; which is the Encouragement that all are to expect, who go in Search of a *North-West* Passage, from such Neighbours. This appeared still more plainly, when at last, partly by Fear, partly by other Means, the Governor was prevailed upon, to give the *Indians* leave to furnish us with Eight or Ten Carcases of Venison; for which we paid above ten Times the Value of what they cost him in Salt Provisions.

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THE whole Month of *January* wore the settled Face of Winter; for except that sometimes the Weather was dark and tempestuous, with vast Drifts of Snow, and at other Times pretty clear, the Frost was constant and intense; Partridges and Rabbits, of which hitherto we had a tolerable Plenty, began to grow very scarce. Our People too sickened apace, and there was hardly any of our Ship's Crew, that was not either more or less afflicted with the Scurvy; insomuch, that by the End of the Month, the People of the *California*, buried two, and we one of that Distemper. In the Month of *February*, the Weather continued much the same, 'till towards the middle; then it grew somewhat milder, and the Wind setting to the South West, the Snow thawed very fast: From thence we had changeable Weather; sometimes very tolerable, and at others, cold to an intense Degree. In this Time, one of the Men

belonging to the *California* died; and one of our People, met with an unlucky Accident, by the unexpected going off of a Musket, which tore away three of his Fingers. On the 23d of this Month, Orders were given to cut the Ice from about our Ships; which was performed with Ice Chissels, and Pickaxes; It was believed, that this would have been a most grievous Labour; but when it came to be undertaken, it was soon found, that they were not froze to the Bottom, so that it turned to a Kind of wholesome and pleasant Exercise; at which the People wrought a little while every Day, and yet with equal Ease and Expedition it was effected. Our Guns, and most other Things of considerable Weight, were sent down to *York-Fort*, upon a large Sledge, that the Ship might prove the lighter, when the Ice was broke up; which, from Appearances at that Time we very speedily expected.

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IN the Month of *March*, we had a Specimen of every Kind of Weather, that is ever met with in this Country: Sometimes, it was not only temperate, but, in some Degree, warm; at others, cold again as ever; but for the most Part moderate and pleasant; so that the Snow melted wherever it was exposed to the Sun; and towards the End of the Month, some Herbage began to peep out on the Banks, fronting Southwards. By this Time also, the Rivers and Plains were covered with Water; so that we were very apprehensive that the Ice would break up suddenly and violently, a Thing not at all uncommon in those Parts; and therefore to prevent the ill Consequences, with which we foresaw it might be attended, Orders were given, for getting every thing in the Ship ready; and after she had been well warmed with Fires, a sufficient Number of Men, with proper Officers, were put on board, to take care of her. We had another Man died this

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Month, and several of our People were in a very bad Way; but the Crew of the *California* were, by this Time, all in a fair Way of Recovery.

APRIL opened in such a manner, as in a good Measure freed us from the Terrors we were under about the Ice breaking; for the Winds came about to the North East, which, together with Snow and Hail, brought a sharp Frost, and nipping cold Weather; Things however not at all unusual in that Country at this Season. But notwithstanding this Change, we did not in the least repent the Precautions that we had taken, as knowing them to be very rational, and, consequently, very expedient. In order to make the Reader sensible of this, it is requisite to observe, that when warm Weather comes in sooner than usual, in the Country about *Hudson's-Bay*, the Snow in the Southern Parts melts, and comes down in great Floods, tearing up the Ice, before it is thoroughly rotten, till it meets with such a Resistance, as checks it for a Time, and then the upper Ice, and the Water in which it floats stops, 'till it acquires such a Weight, as breaks up all by main Force, and laying the adjacent Lands under Water, carries away Banks, Trees, and whatever else opposes it's Fury. This is what the People, who reside there call a *Deluge*; and for this Reason it is very unsafe to let a Ship winter, where there runs any Stream; the Effects of which, tho' we happily escaped, yet that ought to be no Precedent; for the Caution before mentioned is certainly very well founded.

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ON the 15th of *April*, we buried one of our Men: He had been a great Dram-Drinker,¹⁰ and therefore the Scurvy would not spare him. The Ground was so hard froze, that it was, generally speaking, three or four Days Work to sink a Grave; but when the Corpses were once fairly laid in it,

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10 Dram-Drinker. One who habitually drinks spirits.

they remained safe and uncorrupt; and are so like to remain, unless some great Alteration happens in that Climate, to the World's-End.

ON the 18th, the Weather began to mend, and the Wind coming about to the South, we had a fine gentle Shower of Rain, a Thing we had not seen for six Months past, and therefore the more welcome. The Fowls too, after an Absence of seven Months, began to visit us: I mean such as are proper to this Country; and with them came Abundance of Wild-Fowl, of all those Sorts that are common in any of the Northern Parts of *Europe*; such as Geese, Ducks, &c. We had likewise a great Flight of small Birds, mostly of a dark unpleasing Colour; but the Sweetness of their Notes sufficiently compensated whatever was amiss in their Plumage, and made their Company equally harmonious and agreeable.

WE had after this a short Return of Winter, attended by bleak Winds, hard Frosts, much Snow, with very stormy and tempestuous Weather, which lasted to about the 6th of *May*; then the warm Weather returned again, and the Creek, where the Ships lay, was quite clear of Ice, that wore away imperceptibly, tho' the River continued to be still hard froze, which drove the Fish into the Creek, where we caught Plenty of them with our Nets. The RESOLUTION (for that was the Name we bestowed upon our Long-Boat, when lengthened) was now compleatly finished, so that we launched her on the 10th, to the great Joy of all who wished well to the Discovery, and who formed to themselves vast Hopes of what, by the Help of this Vessel, might be performed. From the 8th to the 16th, we had changeable Weather, attended with keen Frost, Snow, Sleet,¹¹ Hail, and Rain, which froze as it fell,

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11 <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sleet>

in such a manner, that all the Trees were covered with Ice. On the 16th, the Ice in the Channel of *Hayes's* River, gave Way, and floated down gently with the Stream. Our People were all this Time constantly employed in making the Ships fit to go down the River; and accordingly, on the 29th, by the Help of a very high Tide, occasioned by a North West Wind, we warped to the very Mouth of the Creek, where we grounded, and lay there until the 2d of *June*, and it was with no small Labour, joined to the extraordinary good Fortune of higher Tides than usual, that we got off so soon.

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...

<https://archive.org/details/voyagetohudsonsb00inelli/page/280/mode/2up>

THE Wind blowing from the South, we were detained in the *Welcome* till the 19th, when it shifted, and we took the Advantage of sailing Southward; but as it grew tempestuous from the North West, and the *Resolution* which we had towed ever since we left the *Wager*, being both a Hindrance to the Ship, and hazardous to the People who were in her, it was judged more expedient to take all Things out of her, and turn her a-drift, than to remain in this Condition any longer, which was accordingly done. We had fine Weather on the 20th and 21st, but as we were at some Distance from *Cary-Swan's-Nest*, we made no Use of the Season, with Respect to the Trial of the Tide there; tho' as the Reader must remember, this was amongst the Number of the Things proposed as necessary to be done in the last Resolution.

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As the Weather grew afterwards very indifferent, a Council was called on board the *California*, in which a definitive Resolution

was taken to bear away, without farther Delay for *England*, and was put in Execution immediately. On the 27th we saw Cape *Pembroke*,¹² on the Eastern Coast of *Hudson's Bay*. On the 28th, we passed the Island of *Mansel*,¹³ and sailed by some Ice, of which we had many large Pieces in View, 'till we arrived over against Cape *Charles*. We entered *Hudson's Strait*¹⁴ on the 29th, and had very pleasant and warm Weather, which lasted 'till the 3d of *September*, and then it grew foul again, having at the same Time a strong Wind from the Eastward. We fell in on the 5th with two of the *Hudson's Bay Company's*¹⁵ Ships, with whom we resolved to keep Company, yet were separated from them in the Night of the 6th, but were lucky enough to rejoin them the next Day. The uncomfortable Weather we had, made so chiefly by the thick and noisome Fogs, proved the Cause, that many of our People began now to relapse into their old Distemper the Scurvy, which was the more unfortunate at this Juncture, as we were then in the most dangerous Navigation of all those Seas, occasioned by the Narrowness of the Straits, the Want of Soundings, huge Mountains of Ice, which may be very well compared to floating Rocks, and the dismal dark Weather, which renders it so very difficult to avoid them. Yet frightful and shocking as these Circumstances are, it is not long before they become so familiar as not to affect us much, and the Danger is so far lessened by keeping a constant Watch, and proper Discipline amongst the Seamen, that one seldom hears of any melancholy Accident. This is the more manifest from a Fact, the Truth of which is indisputable; and that is, the *Hud-*

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12 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cape_Pembroke_\(Nunavut\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cape_Pembroke_(Nunavut))

13 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mansel_Island
<https://thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/mansel-island>

14 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hudson_Strait
<https://thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/hudson-strait>

15 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hudson%27s_Bay_Company
<https://thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/hudsons-bay-company>

san's Bay Company's Ships, returning Year after Year without any Disaster; from whence perhaps we may infer, that where constant and continual Danger excites perpetual Attention, it thereby alters it's Nature, and becomes, if I may be allowed the Expression, the Cause of Safety.

...

Additions to footnote 9:

Cartier (Winter 1535-1536):

“One day our captain [Cartier], seeing the sickness so violent and his people so smitten with it, being gone outside of the fort and walking by himself upon the ice, beheld a band of folks coming from Stadaconé, in the which was Dom Agaya, whom the captain had seen, only ten or twelve days before, very sick with the sickness which his people had; for he had one of his legs as big at the knee as a child of two years, and all the sinews of it shrunken, his teeth lost and spoiled, and his gums putrid and corrupted. The captain, seeing the said Dom Agaya sound and well, was glad, hoping to know from him how he was cured, so as to give aid and succor to his men. When they were arrived near the fort, the captain asked him how he was cured of his sickness; the which Dom Agaya responded that he was cured by the juice and refuse of the **leaves of a tree**, and that it was the only remedy for the sickness... They call the said tree in their tongue *amedda*. Soon after the captain had some of the beverage made in order to have the sick drink of it... Shortly after they had drunken of it they received benefit, which was found to be a real and evident miracle; for all the sick, of whatever they were infected, after having drunken of it two or three times, recovered health and vigor... After this was seen and understood there was such strife for the said medicine that they would have killed themselves to see who first should have it; so that a tree as big and as tall as any tree I ever saw was used up in less than eight days, which had such effect that if all the doctors of Lorraine and Montpellier had been there, with all the drugs of Alexandria, they could not have done so much in a year as the said tree did in six days; for it profited us so much that all those who would use it recovered health and soundness, thanks to God.”

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17348074> Cartier's second voyage; Baxter p.194-196

James Lind (1757):

“The antiscorbutic virtue of the fir was, like many other of our best medicines, accidentally discovered in *Europe*. When the *Swedes* carried on a war against the *Muscovites*, almost all the soldiers of their army were destroyed by the true marsh or marine scurvy, having rotten gums, rigid tendons, &c. But a stop was put to the progress of this disease, by the advice of *Erbenius* the King's physician, with **a simple decoction of fir-tops**; by which the most deplorable cases were perfectly recovered, and the rest of the soldiers prevented from falling into it. It also proved an excellent gargle for the putrid gums.”

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy00lind/page/176/mode/2up> Lind p.176

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/xc2t7736/items?canvas=200>

“In the year 1736 two squadrons of ships fitted out by the court of *Russia*, were obliged to winter in *Siberia*. One commanded by *Demetrius Laptiew*, not far from the mouth of the river *Lena*, was attacked by the scurvy. The men in their distress by chance found near them this tree growing in the mountains, and experienced it to have a most surprising antiscorbutic virtue. At the same time while *Alexius Tschirikow* was passing the winter in the river *Judoma*, where it runs into the river *Maja*, a considerable number of his men were dreadfully afflicted with that disease. After various fruitless attempts to discover a remedy able to put a stop to this cruel disaster, he at length accidentally hit also upon **the pines** which grew plentifully on the mountains, by which all his men were recovered in a few days. In some the medicine proved gently laxative, in others it affected the body so mildly that its operation was scarce sensible.”

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy00lind/page/176/mode/2up> Lind p.177

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/xc2t7736/items?canvas=201>